

Final Report of the FAIRAgro Incubator Project in IAM4NFDI

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Report Details

1. Introduction

The FAIRAgro consortium, as part of the NFDI initiative, has the objective of facilitating agrosystems research by providing a range of services, including internal services, such as Nextcloud, as well as community services, including the FAIRAgro Middleware, the Search Hub and the Scientific Workflow Infrastructure (SciWIn). To ensure seamless integration and secure access control, an Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) is required. This incubator project was conducted to evaluate the four Community AAI (CAAI) solutions provided by IAM4NFDI, and to select the most suitable option that meets the specific requirements of FAIRAgro.

2. Methodology

2.1 Evaluation process

The evaluation process consisted of the following steps:

1. Familiarization with Community AAIs.
2. Identification of FAIRAgro's authentication and authorization requirements.
3. Evaluation of the four CAAs against the requirements.
4. Integration of the FAIRAgro Nextcloud instance with the most suitable CAAI solutions.

5. Test and feedback loops within FAIRAgro to discuss the results.
6. Selection of a CAAI solution based on the results.

2.2 Technical setup for evaluation

FAIRAgro Nextcloud runs as a docker container inside a Kubernetes Cluster, physically located within the HPC Cluster at the ZALF institute in Muencheberg (Mark). Helm and ArgoCD are used to manage and deploy the Nextcloud container in Kubernetes. This combination provides reliability/scalability/tolerance and is considered the current IT-best-practice in the provision of critical services to consumers. To enhance the user's experience with Nextcloud, we also evaluated the "Office solutions" CollaboraOnline and OnlyOffice, and selected OnlyOffice Extended.

In order to establish a connection between the Nextcloud and the CAAI, it is possible to utilise the protocols SAML or OIDC. SAML (Security Assertion Markup Language) is an XML-based protocol used for Single Sign-On (SSO) in enterprise environments, allowing users to authenticate once and access multiple services. It works by exchanging security assertions between identity and service providers to confirm the user's identity. OIDC (OpenID Connect) is a more recent authentication protocol built on OAuth 2.0, which is commonly used for SSO in web and mobile applications. It provides user identity information via JSON Web Tokens (JWT).

3. Results

3.1 Short overview of the IAM community AAI solutions

Community AAIs are web platforms that enable a community (i.e. an NFDI consortium) to manage its members and associated data, as well as the access to various services and resources. This includes in particular handling Virtual Organisation (VO) and group memberships, as well as managing user attributes. IAM4NFDI has proposed four software products for consideration: AcademicID by GWDG, didmos by DAASI International, RegApp by KIT, and Helmholtz AAI by HIFIS, which uses Unity (<https://doc.nfdi-aai.de/>).

There are two deployment models available: multi-tenant and individual instance. In the multi-tenant model, the Community AAI is hosted and maintained by the provider, with the consortium acting as a tenant. The consortium assigns administrators, who have extended permissions, primarily for managing group memberships. This model has a predefined system setup with limited customization options. Consulting, support and operational services for the multi-tenant CAAIs is financed as a service for the NFDI consortia within the framework of the IAM4NFDI project, albeit to a limited extent. Conversely, the individual instance model requires the consortium to host the platform on its own responsibility and taking care of common operational aspects, like backup and monitoring. This approach offers greater flexibility for advanced use cases, as the platform can be fully customized to meet specific needs. The financing of an individual CAAI instance is not covered by the IAM4NFDI project; in such cases, a separate operating agreement is concluded with the CAAI operator, which may result in additional costs for the consortium.

3.2 FAIRragro requirements

Access control options: FAIRragro will provide a range of services. These comprise consortium-internal services such as Nextcloud, Zammad and LimeSurvey as well as external FAIRragro services that are made available to the community, i.e. the FAIRragro Middleware, the Search Hub and SciWIn. For the internal services, the organisational structure of the consortium needs to be mapped as groups or roles, respectively. This is necessary to ensure that access rights can be assigned accordingly. In the context of the community services, the primary focus pertains to the management of access control for restricted datasets. It is required to establish a mechanism that enables the regulation of access at the dataset level.

IdPs relevant for FAIRragro: Regarding identity providers (IdPs), the DFN-AAI (<https://www.aai.dfn.de/>) and Edu-ID (Bacharach et al. 2022), as soon as available, are intended to be used as IdPs for the Community AAI. While a number of FAIRragro institutions are part of the DFN-AAI, it should be noted that this is not the case for all of them. Indeed, only 13 out of 31 institutions are participating. Consequently, in addition to the DFN-AAI, further options must be considered. Furthermore, when considering the external FAIRragro Services their utilisation by users without an institutional affiliation must be taken into account. Potential alternatives to the DFN-AAI could be social IdPs (e.g. ORCID) or local accounts at the AAI.

Features: In terms of the desired features, the ability to provide multi-factor authentication (MFA) is considered advantageous, particularly for administrative users. Furthermore, the integration of account linking functionality is regarded as a beneficial feature.

Deployment: Both on-premise deployment and hosting by a different provider are possible, as long as no additional financial costs are incurred.

3.3 Evaluation of the CAAs against FAIRragro requirements

First, the requirement of controlling access to restricted data sets was reviewed. This revealed that two CAAI solutions, namely AcademicID and RegApp, intend to utilise a didmos component, the Policy Decision Point (PDP), to fulfil this function. In order to avoid too much complexity, it seems reasonable to use didmos directly in this case. However, the PDP is not included in the didmos multi-tenant instance and thus, the operation of a individual instance would be necessary. The Helmholtz AAI team has communicated via email that they are collaborating on this issue with PUNCH4NFDI. They will use software component called “attribute authority” to store additional information, e.g. the dataset access. Consequently, AcademicID and RegApp were not subjected to further detailed investigation, but didmos and Helmholtz AAI were examined more closely.

For this purpose, VOs at the multi-tenant systems were requested from the operators. After these were set up, the connected IdPs, in particular the available alternatives to the DFN-AAI, as well as the user and group management were examined. In the case of didmos, DFN-AAI and Edu-ID are available as IdPs. Local accounts are provided as an alternative. However, the login process with DFN-AAI does not always function as intended. The functionality depends on the attributes that the institution transmits to the CAAI. In case that the attributes do not meet the necessary requirements (<https://doc.nfdi-aai.de/attributes/#attributes-needed-by-the-community-aais>), the login process is not successful. The Helmholtz AAI provides, in addition to the DFN-AAI, ORCID and Google as IdPs. Henceforth, the Edu-ID will additionally be made available as an IdP. Local accounts are not utilised in this instance. If any attributes are missing, the Helmholtz AAI offers a form in which they can be entered manually. With regard to the account linking feature, the following information was

provided: Didmos is currently engaged in the development of this functionality within another incubator, with its implementation envisaged by 2025. The Helmholtz AAI is technically feasible, and the implementation of the feature is prepared. Both CAAI solutions support two-factor authentication in form of time-based tokens (TOTP) and this method was effective for both. Additionally, email tokens are offered by didmos as a second factor, but this option did not work during testing.

The didmos and Helmholtz AAI systems both offer administrator functionality that includes the management of users and groups. In the didmos system, administrators are allowed to create and delete user accounts and to edit user information. New users can register themselves at the VO. Furthermore, it is possible to import a greater number of users via a CSV file. However, this option has not been tested. A number of user information can be stored, e.g. phone numbers or ORCID. In contrast, the Helmholtz AAI restricts new user registration to invitations only, self-registration is not possible. In this instance, administrators are unable to view or edit user information. The user information stored is limited in scope, including name, email address, eduPersonEntitlement, and Helmholtz affiliation. With regard to roles, a predefined number of possible roles are available for both systems; the definition of new roles is not supported. However, the possibility to create groups is available in both systems. It should be noted that didmos does not support hierarchies for group organisation, a fact that has the potential to cause difficulties in the management of a large number of groups. In contrast, the Helmholtz AAI facilitates the creation of subgroups, thereby enabling a clear group structure.

With regard to deployment, both didmos and the Helmholtz AAI offer multi-tenant instances as a service for the NFDI consortia via IAM4NFDI. Additionally, didmos provides individual instances, which requires funding from the consortium. Helmholtz AAI does not offer the operation of individual instances.

In addition, the connection of the FAIRragro Nextcloud instance to the CAAs was tested. The recommendation by didmos was to utilise SAML for this purpose. The establishment of the aforementioned connection was successful. After an adjustment by didmos, the transfer of group memberships to Nextcloud was also made possible. In contrast, the operators of the Helmholtz AAI recommended using OIDC. However, despite the provision of support by the Helmholtz AAI team, the connection could not be established, as Nextcloud does not transmit the HTTP Basic Auth header that is required by Unity and to try and get it working would have involved considerable rewriting and extension of existing code.

	didmos	Helmholtz AAI
User and group management		
Management of users and groups	yes	yes
Hierarchies for groups	no	yes
IdPs		
DFN-AAI	yes ¹	yes
Edu-ID	yes	yes ²
Google	no	yes
ORCID	no	yes

Local accounts	yes	no
Features		
Access control for restricted data sets	yes	yes
Multi-factor authentication	yes	yes
Account linking	yes ²	yes ²
Deployment		
Multi-tenant instance	yes	yes
Individual instance	yes ³	no
Connection to FAIRagro Nextcloud	SAML, successful	OIDC, but not successful

Table 1: Overview of the Evaluation Results Against FAIRagro Requirements.

¹ If not all required attributes are provided, login with DFN-AAI fails.

² In development.

³ Associated with additional costs for the consortium.

4. Conclusion and Next Steps

Two of the four CAAI solutions, Academic ID and RegApp, were excluded by the requirement of access control to restricted datasets. As these two solutions intend to use a didmos component, it seems reasonable to use didmos directly in order to avoid unnecessary complexity. The Helmholtz AAI was precluded by the fact that the connection to the FAIRagro Nextcloud did not work, and any effort in overcoming this limitation would have involved considerable expenditure in scarce resources. This left only didmos as a possible candidate. Due to the FAIRagro requirements, an individual instance would be necessary here. However, due to financial constraints, it is not feasible to consider the didmos offer.

Therefore, after evaluating the four CAAI solutions, the FAIRagro consortium decided to operate its own Keycloak instance and use this as Community AAI. Nonetheless, it is planned to use one of the CAAI solutions, most likely didmos, as IdP for Keycloak, thereby enabling the connection to the DFN-AAI and Edu-ID. The development of the CAAs proposed by IAM4NFDI will be continuously followed and a switch to one of the solutions may be considered at a later stage.

References

Bacharach, G. et al. (2022) „Whitepaper der ZKI AG edu-ID zur Verortung des Konzepts einer edu-ID in der aktuellen Landschaft digitaler Identitäten in Deutschland und Europa“. Zenodo. doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7425176.

Abbreviations

IPK Leibniz Institute of Plant Genetics and Crop Plant Research

SGN Senckenberg Society for Nature Research

ZALF Leibniz Centre for Agricultural Landscape Research

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